

Ethovision: Juvenile Reciprocal Social Interaction

- Click New → create a file name → then OK
- Go to Experiment Settings
 - Number of subjects: 2 → right-click to rename Subject 1 “Experimental” and Subject 2 “Stimulus”
 - Tracked Features: center-point, nose-point, tail-base detection

Arena Settings

- Go to Arena Settings 1 → Arena Settings 1 → then click Browse
- Open the video and click Grab
 - Double-check the bin wasn’t moved during the video, then return to video start with ID card/ruler
- Select 1. Draw Scale to Calibrate → draw length of ruler → type 25 (cm) → OK
- Select 2. Shape and Draw Arena → select Create Closed Polyline button on top bar
 - Click on each corner of the arena at the top of the bin walls, and double-click final/4th corner
 - Make sure the arena covers the walls and do *NOT* let the arena touch areas outside of the bin
- Rename “Arena Settings 1” to the animal ID number of the experimental mouse in the video

Trial Control Settings

- Go to Trial Control Settings 1 → Trial Control Settings 1
 - Select, right-click, and delete first Condition box → check box next to Time
 - In the time condition box → change condition name to “Start” → select After and enter the number of seconds when both mice (experimental and stimulus) first appear in the video and the experimenter is also out of view
 - Make sure there are 20 minutes of video after the mouse’s start time
 - Connect all boxes in timeline with arrows; the “Start” time condition box should be in the second position
 - In the second time condition box → Settings → change condition name to “Stop” → set to stop after 20 minutes
 - Rename “Trial Control Settings 1” to the animal ID number of the experimental mouse in the video

Detection Settings

- Go to Detection Settings 1 → Detection Settings 1
 - On the right, if necessary, click Select Video → choose the video corresponding to that trial
 - Click to part of video showing both mice
 - Go to the Advanced tab to the right, and click the black bar under Marker of Experimental
 - Click the back of the experimental mouse on the bluest part of its back → Ok
 - Click the black bar for Marker of Stimulus
 - Click the back of the stimulus mouse on the pinkest part of its back → Ok
 - Also under Advanced, select Gray Scaling from the drop-down menu → set the range from 0-45 → select Rodents/For Occlusions from the drop-down
 - Smoothing → use default settings
 - Subject contour: check the Contour Erosion box and select 3 pixels, check Contour Dilation and select 4 pixels, make sure the drop-down says Erode first, then dilate
 - Subject size minimum/maximum:
 - For 25 fps videos: use 3,000 min - 18,000 max; for 10 fps videos, see NOR protocol
 - Click Edit enter min/max numbers → Close (make sure they both registered) → Save

- Make sure the tracking looks good
- On the left, right-click Detection Settings 1
 - If all videos have identical lighting conditions and frame rate, one detection entry can be used for all; name it “Detection for all”
 - Caution: you cannot edit detection settings that are applied to other acquired trials. If one, or a few trials need detection alterations, create new detection entries for them.
 - Detection settings could also be done using automated set-up—to use this method, trace a box around both mice (from the tail base to the tip of the nose) for each trial, adjust Marker of Experimental and Stimulus for each, check the tracking, and rename each detection setting with the experimental animal ID number

Click File → Save after each set of settings to avoid losing work if Ethovision crashes

Repeat for all other animals:

- Click on previous animal ID under Arena Settings: right-click → duplicate → name as next animal ID → click Grab Background Image Button in bottom right → find video → Grab → adjust/resize/redraw arenas and rulers as needed → click Validate Setup
- Click on previous animal ID under Trial Control Settings: right-click → duplicate and name with next animal ID → adjust the delay time in the “Start” box for the mice in that video
 - Apply the new settings only in the current Trial Control Settings
- *Only if using multiple detection settings*: Click on previous Animal ID under Detection Settings: right-click → duplicate and name with next animal ID → use automated set-up as described above

Trial List

- Trial List → Add Trials → # of Animals → Ok
- Add Variable → rename animal ID#
- Add Videos → Alphabetical → Browse → select all videos and import them in order from same folder
- Make list in numerical order of animal ID#s → copy and paste into blank columns →
 - Each row should have the same animal ID#s all across

Acquisition

- Acquisition → Acquisition → Track All Planned → Ready for Start (red circle button) → videos are analyzed
- Track editor → check if trials need arrow swaps (this is likely); refer to arrow swap protocol
 - **Swap arrows** for any trials in which arrows are backwards some of the time

Analysis

- Go to Analysis → Analysis Profile 1 → Analysis Profile 1
 - Under Social → click box next to Proximity:
 - In Proximity Threshold: 1.5cm
 - Not in Proximity Threshold: 2cm
 - Calculate Statistics For: In Proximity (only)
 - In the same window, under Body Points tab:
 - Nose-point (only); in the drop-down menu: Each point
 - In the same window, under Receivers tab:
 - Stimulus (only); in drop-down menu: Each Subject
 - Body Points: Nose-point (only); in drop-down menu: Each Point

- In the same window, under Trial Statistics tab:
 - Frequency + Cumulative Duration (only)
- Click Add → right-click on Proximity and rename to “Nose to Nose”
- Make new proximity variables for Nose to Body:
 - Right-click Nose-to-Nose variable from list → duplicate → rename to “Nose to Body”
 - Double-click Nose to Body variable to change settings
 - Under the Receivers tab:
 - Stimulus (only); in drop-down menu: Each Subject
 - Body Points: Center-point (only); in drop-down menu: Each Point
- Make new proximity variables for Nose to Tail:
 - Right-click Nose-to-Body variable from list → duplicate → rename to “Nose to Tail”
 - Double-click Nose to Tail variable to change settings
 - Under the Receivers tab:
 - Stimulus (only); in drop-down menu: Each Subject
 - Body Points: Tail-base (only); in drop-down menu: Each Point
- Under Social → click box next to Relative Movement:
 - Under Body Points tab:
 - Center-point (only); in drop-down menu: Each point
 - Under Receivers tab:
 - Subjects: Stimulus (only); in drop-down menu: Each subject
 - Body points: Center-point (only); in drop-down menu: Each point
 - Under Trial Statistics tab:
 - Cumulative Duration (only)
 - Click Add
- Under Social → click box next to Body Contact:
 - Under Body Contact tab:
 - Body contact (only)
 - Under Trial Statistics tab:
 - Cumulative Duration (only)
 - Click Add

Add Data and Analysis Profiles

- Right-click Data Profile 1 → duplicate and rename “Distance Between Subjects”
 - In the Result 1 box in the center screen, click Settings → click Results per time bin
 - Length: 5 min
 - Check Ignore last time bin if incomplete → OK
- Right-click Analysis Profile 1 → duplicate → rename to “Distance Between Subjects”
 - Under Social → click box next to Distance Between Subjects:
 - Under Body Points tab:
 - Center-point (only)
 - Under Receivers tab:

- Subjects: Stimulus (only); in drop-down menu
 - Center-point (only)
- Under Trial Statistics tab:
 - Mean (only)
 - Click Add

Results

- Statistics and Charts:
 - For Data Profile 1 & Analysis profile 1 (on drop-down menus) → click Calculate → click Export Data and save file
 - For Distance between subjects & Distance between subjects (on drop-down menus) → click Calculate → click Export Data and save file